

What digital humanists don't know about scholarly editing; what scholarly editors don't know about the digital world

I am a simple person, and when I first started thinking of this conference, I had a very simple idea: let's just get as many digital humanists and as many textual scholars as we can within one room for three days and let's see what happens. It's possible that no area of the humanities has as much to benefit from the digital revolution as textual scholarship, and digital humanities may have more to gain from textual scholarship than any other area. These two disciplines have already had a lot to say to each other. We have three days now to talk to each other. But every conversation, we all know, carries this danger: when we think we understand the other person but actually, we don't. Even more dangerous, I think, is the situation when not only does the other person think he or she understands, but you think the other person understands you -- but actually, they do not. Then, you are both really in trouble.

Let's start with the digital humanist side of the conversation. What do digital humanists think they know about textual scholarship, and how are they wrong? I think digital humanists have two fundamental misconceptions about textual scholarship. The first misconception is this: that textual scholarship is all about what John Unsworth calls the 'primitives' of humanist scholarship: discovering, annotating, comparing, referring, sampling, illustrating, and representing. We find texts, we record information about them, we create ways of representing the text, we compare the texts, we annotate them. Yes, this is correct. Yes, we do catalogue manuscripts, we describe them, we transcribe them, we collate them. All these are indeed parts of our work. And all these are highly suitable cases for computer treatment, which is why digital humanists are so fond of textual scholars. But it is an error to think that these activities completely describe textual scholarship. They do not. You can do these things and create a digital archive. But if this is all you do, you will not create an edition. An edition requires that you make decisions: who is the edition made for? What text, or texts, should it present? How should these texts be prepared; who should do the preparation; how should the texts be presented; what should be the basis of the texts presented? These decisions are often difficult, even controversial. They are usually made by a single editor, or by a small group of scholars. Clearly, the editors who make these decisions need the catalogues, the transcriptions, the collations; they need the digital archives that digital humanists have become so good at making. In turn, the digital archives must be shaped by the needs of textual scholars, so that the materials they make are fit for use.

Hence: the common first error made by digital humanists, -- and, I fear, by many editors: that the needs of textual scholars, and indeed the interests of readers, can be perfectly served by digital archives. They cannot. An edition is an argument about a text. We need arguments; without arguments, our archives are inert bags of words and images.

This overconfidence by digital humanists, that they believe that they understand what editing is, leads to the second common error digital humanists make. It is this: that digital humanists may usefully collaborate with textual scholars. After twenty years of working with my digital humanist hat on, as a collaborator with textual scholars, I can tell you now: this collaboration is a mistake. We have had to work this way for two decades because the digital tools needed to make a scholarly edition have been so difficult to use that no sane editor -- indeed, no sane person -- would want to use them. We had to work this way, too, because we needed to discover what digital tools could do. But we should seek, as soon as we can, to end this collaboration. Textual scholars should not need a digital humanist to be able to catalogue manuscripts, to make transcriptions, to compare texts, to analyze the differences between texts. Now, I put my textual scholar hat back on, and assert: I want to do these things myself. I want to decide what to transcribe, how, and what should be compared, and then I want to do it myself -- or delegate it to other people who are interested and expert in the text. I want tools to do this work, certainly, and digital humanists will be needed to make these tools. But I should be able to use these tools directly, myself, without unreasonable expenditure of time or money or effort, to make the editions I want to make. I do not want a digital humanist as a collaborator, to mediate this work: I want to engage with it directly, myself and with others like me. And what I want to do, myself, every editor, everyone who wants to make an edition, should be able to do. I said earlier, that the most dangerous misconceptions are those which are shared. In the last decades, too many editors, myself included, have subscribed to both notions: that digital archives may stand in place of editions (or might even be editions -- social editions, perhaps); and that editors cannot do this work on their own. It is time to assert the value of editions in the digital age, as fundamental discourses about the texts which are important to us. It is time for us, as editors, to take back control over the texts we make, and how we make them. Digital humanists should get out of textual scholarship: and if they will not, textual scholars should throw them out.

The misconceptions do not lie just on one side. There is one thing scholarly editors do not know about the digital world and which they have to learn. It is this: for the editions they make to go on living, to be useful and to continue to be useful, to go on being read for decades and centuries, the editor must give up control. This is actually the reverse of what is the case for the print world, where the publisher's need for exclusive copyright and the editor's desire for control join in a cosy conspiracy, issuing in a pristine unchanging printed book. Editors, hear this: if you want your digital edition to be used by others, to become the centre of other people's work, to be transfigured over and over into bright new forms of scholarship, if you have to release it without restriction, to permit both commercial and non-commercial work, to license the making of any and all derivative works. Scholars, I know from bitter experience, find this very difficult to do. Years, decades and more, of close devotion to their text leads to it becoming 'my text' (or, 'my manuscript'). At the least, they do not want their mortal enemy (and every scholar wears his enemies as a badge of distinction) to use their text in his or her own edition. Again, a cosy conspiracy reinforces this short-sighted choice: the digital humanities centre which

collaborated in the making of the edition would like to keep exclusive control of the text, to use as coin towards its own continued funding. Editors, just say no to this. Grant funders too have been far too forgiving of this attitude. I said a few minutes ago that we textual scholars should take control of what we do. But if what we do is continue to make materials which we treat as our private property, while pretending that they are available to everyone, we will drive ourselves and our editions into a cul-de-sac. We have to open up what we do to others. We may think others may misinterpret, misunderstand and distort what we make – but the only edition which is never misused is the edition which is never used. We need to make the best editions we can: and then, we have to see these editions not as the end of the dialogue, but as moves in a conversation which others will continue.

Here is my purpose in rehearsing this catalogue of errors. In the last decades, we have solved almost all the technical problems associated with the making of editions. We can transcribe, encode, capture images, link images and text, compare, analyze, and present, all in digital form. We can now invite others to join us in this work, in huge numbers perhaps, so that many hands may make light and pleasant work. For years, in the early days of the marriage of digital methods and textual scholarship, our choices were severely limited by what was possible. Our choices are no longer so circumscribed: rather, we now have all the choices we always had as scholarly editors plus now all the choices digital technology gives us. So, what choices should we make? Where should we put our resources? What models should we aim at?

Rather than try to decide these choices, I'd like to set out some assertions, which might help us towards these decisions. First, what we decide to do depends on what we think a scholarly edition is. There has been a great deal of rhetoric, some of it from myself, the last decades about how scholarly editions and editing have been fundamentally changed by the digital turn. So let me say it plainly. I don't think there has been any such change. A scholarly edition is still, as it has been for centuries, an argument about a text. The fundamental players in this argument are still documents, works, and the editor's interpretation of them. The editor is the editor, and not a "facilitator". There are still many more readers than editors, and most readers do not want to be editors. Certainly, there have been changes – most of them, I think, for the better. The materials upon which editions are based may be far more accessible, and the roots of the edition in the materials far better articulated. The editor's choices may be examined much more closely, and editors accordingly more humble about their choices. Particularly, we are seeing the rise of open collaborations, as editions become grounded in communities of individuals who contribute to their making, under the leadership of editors. We may also see materials made for an edition taken and repurposed in new editions, even against the original edition, in long-running arguments about the text. We are seeing many new tools, and we need yet more, particularly for analyzing and visualizing variant texts. However, some things we are not seeing, and we should not expect to see. We will not see 'social text editions' and we will not see 'social editions.'

Here is what we should do, then. We should work towards a future where anyone who wants to be an editor has, fit and ready for their hands, the tools for themselves to make the editions they want. Included in this toolset should be the ability to invite others to contribute, and to allow others to invite themselves to contribute. In this future, parts of the edition, and the materials upon which it stands, may be endlessly and continually repurposed by others. For this to happen, we need far better systems for enabling the discovery and reuse of editorial materials. Particularly, we need agreements on conventions for naming things: for naming documents, the works they instance, the texts of works within the documents, and all their parts. We need a real commitment to real open texts, really available for others to use and alter and hand on to others, and not the feeble gestures towards openness with which most projects satisfy themselves.

It comes down, in the end, towards our vision of what we want. We can carry on as we are: with a few extremely expensive digital scholarly edition projects, made by the collaboration between a very textual scholars and a very few digital humanists, leaving everyone else to work as best as they can with inadequate tools: putting editions and their materials into wikis, into blogs, or into closed proprietary systems, or into a range of free systems typically using home-brewed or no markup at all. The few good materials will be fantastically expensive to make, and will sit in their own interfaces inaccessible to everyone else; the many poorer materials will be effectively invisible, and of limited value. Put this way, this sounds crazy. But that is what we are doing now, and powerful traditional and institutional forces are pushing us to continue in this direction. This model suits the traditional way scholars think about what we do: we would all like to be at the helm of one of these privileged editions, or to be running a digital humanities centre which hosts them. Just to give a single instance of what is wrong with this model: the Transcribe Bentham project is wonderful, and rightly praised for many things. But consider this. The cost of Transcribe Bentham is over a million dollars, just reckoning on the two major tranches of funding it has received to now. So far the project has transcribed around 5000 of 10000 manuscript pages. Now, you could have had those pages transcribed in the Phillipines for a total cost of around \$50,000 – or, if you really wanted to have everything checked and thoroughly controlled, say \$100,000 at most. I don't think we can afford many more Transcribe Bentham projects.

We don't have to work this way. We might have many more editions made directly by scholars, who form all kinds of new partnerships with readers using all the social tools now available to us, with more readers themselves becoming editors. There should be an unbroken continuum, between the multiple resources created by libraries as they produce and put online more and more images of the manuscripts and books, through the massive online records, with all their flawed OCR, made by Google and others of these materials, then through to the scholarly editions we might build within and on top of all these materials, where every word is scrutinized, every decision weighed, and where our aim is not just to record, not just to present, but to understand. We have great work to do, and there are ways digital humanists

and textual scholars can help each other. However, I argue that we need to look at just where we are, where we are heading, and ask ourselves: is there a better way. I think there is, and I hope this conference starts us out along this better way. I think we should begin, as textual scholars, by declaring exactly what it is we do: we do textual scholarship. We may use digital humanities to be better textual scholars, but we do not pretend to be digital humanists. In return, digital humanists might also declare: we do digital humanities, and we try to help textual scholars to be better textual scholars through digital humanities, but we do not pretend to be textual scholars.